

Centrality-Informed Contextual Experience (CICE): A conceptual framework for human-centred park spatial analysis

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Summary

Urban parks are essential public spaces for improving environmental quality and promoting well-being. The spatial design of parks has long ignored users' diverse needs, while quantitative methods for analysing the complex spatial forms of parks have been insufficient. This study introduces the Centrality-Informed Contextual Experience (CICE) conceptual framework, which incorporates user needs into the traditional spatial-perception-behaviour framework. It discusses the feasibility of using centrality indicators to represent spatial perceptions and user needs. This approach offers valuable insights for urban planners to improve park spatial forms through a human-centred perspective, enhancing spatial efficiency and user experience.

KEYWORDS: Urban parks, Spatial forms, Perception, User needs

1. Introduction

Urban parks are essential in enhancing public well-being by serving as major spaces for recreation and social activities (Peters *et al.*, 2010). Compared to structured urban streets, the spatial forms of parks are more complex (Talen, 2010), influencing people's experience through diverse environmental features and navigational patterns (Zhang *et al.*, 2024). Although the importance of park design has been widely acknowledged, there is a research gap regarding how to improve the spatial forms of different regions in parks to align with user needs and enhance user activities. This study introduces a Centrality-Informed Contextual Experience (CICE) Framework, which integrates centrality measures with user needs and spatial perception analysis.

2. The need for improvement

While the importance of urban parks in enhancing human well-being is increasingly recognised, a gap remains in evaluating and measuring urban parks' design to better align with people's perceptions and needs, leading to unpleasant experiences (Zhao *et al.*, 2024). Current spatial analysis methods primarily focus on geometry, such as spatial distribution and connectivity (You *et al.*, 2022), but often fail to incorporate how individuals perceive and interact with park spaces. Meanwhile, existing research on spatial perception often relies on qualitative methods without quantitative support (McCormack *et al.*, 2010).

The goal of park spatial studies is to optimise spatial forms to enhance activity experiences, health, and overall well-being (Douglas *et al.*, 2017). However, while theories such as the spatial-perception-behaviour framework (Lynch, 1960, p.10) provide a valuable basis, existing approaches lack the quantitative tools to effectively connect spatial forms with subjective perceptions and user activities.

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Achieving designs tailored to user needs demands a deeper understanding of these connections. Therefore, methods capable of quantitatively linking spatial forms, user perceptions, and behavioural patterns are essential. Accessibility, usability, and movement patterns are key factors in ensuring that spatial forms effectively serve people's needs (Goličnik and Ward Thompson, 2010; Zhang et al., 2011). The centrality indicators, with their ability to quantify spatial relationships and link spatial forms to user perceptions, serve as effective measures within the proposed framework to address this gap.

3. The CICE conceptual framework

3.1 Definitions

Concepts are crucial in spatial analysis as they influence how environments are understood, evaluated, and ultimately designed. Uncertainty in definitions can result in differing approaches to understanding and analysis, potentially leading to inconsistent outcomes. In particular, spatial perception and spatial form are concepts with broad definitions, and unclear interpretations can lead to complex and inaccurate outcomes. For example, designing paths to prioritise structural and navigational roles significantly enhances user movement. On the other hand, when paths are primarily emphasised for their aesthetic qualities, such as visual appeal or decorative features, their contribution to the ease of movement is reduced (Lynch, 1960, pp. 48-49). Therefore, clear definitions are essential to accurately analyse the relationship between spatial forms and perception.

Spatial form refers to the arrangement and organisation of physical spaces, emphasising a coherent and integrated structure (Lynch, 1960, p.10). In this study, spatial form is defined as the arrangement and relationships of spatial regions of urban parks, specifically represented through the regional association (reflecting regional complexity and diversity), accessibility (indicating overall convenience), and management of pedestrian movement (focusing on efficient flow).

Spatial perception refers to an individual's experience and interpretation of spatial features in an environment, influenced by accessibility, safety, and cultural context, and closely linked to user behaviour (Jordan and Knoblich, 2004; Wang *et al.*, 2015). This study defines spatial perception as the subjective experience of environmental diversity, accessible perception, and smooth navigation. These perceptions, realised through exploration, dwelling, and interaction, correspond to the needs for diverse activities, convenience, and efficient movement.

3.2 Framework overview

The Centrality-Informed Contextual Experience (CICE) Conceptual Framework (see Figure 1) provides a structured approach to understanding and designing urban parks by addressing the connections between spatial forms, spatial perceptions, user behaviours, and user needs. Urban Design Theory emphasises the role of spatial forms, such as well-defined paths and distinct nodes, in shaping user interactions and movements by providing logical connections (Lynch, 1960, pp. 96-99). The CICE Conceptual Framework addresses a critical gap in traditional theory by incorporating user needs into spatial-perception-behaviour models, emphasising factors from a human-centred perspective. Additionally, it demonstrates the rationality of using centrality indicators to analyse these factors through quantitative methods, offering a more comprehensive approach to spatial analysis.

3.3 Relationships between components

In urban parks, functional facilities like seating, play areas, and water features enhance social interaction and prolonged use (Douglas *et al.*, 2017). While greenery positively affects spatial perception use, the impact of spatial form on environmental cognition is complex, influenced by cultural contexts and social needs (Wang *et al.*, 2015; Douglas *et al.*, 2017). An individual's cognition of the environment is complex, involving multiple dimensions, including spatial structural features, environmental attributes, and psychological benefits (Proulx *et al.*, 2016). Path layouts and region distributions affect perceptions of accessibility, spatial complexity, and navigational efficiency

Figure 1 CICE conceptual framework, source: author

(Lynch, 1960, pp. 47-48, 99). For example, activity diversity is enhanced by well-integrated regions, where clear intersections and connected pathways promote accessibility and efficient movement by ensuring ease of navigation and managing flow to prevent overcrowding (Lynch, 1960, pp. 99,111). The relationships between user needs, spatial perception, and spatial form are central to shaping park activity and behaviour (Wang *et al.*, 2015; Proulx *et al.*, 2016). User needs such as diverse activities, convenience, and efficient movement align with spatial perception factors, including environmental diversity, accessibility, and smooth navigation (Talen, 2010). Similarly, spatial form factors such as regional association, accessibility, and traffic flow influence spatial perceptions (Wang *et al.*, 2015).

3.4 Centralities for spatial form quantification

Centrality measures, as introduced by Freeman (1979), provide a method to analyse spatial forms by identifying key nodes, optimising pathways, and enhancing overall network efficiency in spatial systems. By applying degree centrality to enhance communication activity, closeness centrality to improve efficiency and independence, and betweenness centrality to control flow, planners can better design urban parks to support engagement, accessibility, and pedestrian movement. In park design, nodes with higher degree centrality represent intersections with multiple connections, highlighting zones of frequent user interactions. Nodes with higher closeness centrality are ideal for placing facilities like restrooms, ensuring these amenities are accessible from all parts of the park. High betweenness centrality nodes represent key corridors or junctions managing pedestrian flow.

4. Conclusion

This positioning paper introduces the CICE conceptual framework, which integrates user needs into the traditional spatial-perception-behaviour model, selecting diverse activities, convenience, and efficient movement as key factors to link spatial forms and spatial perception. The study also integrates centrality as a quantitative method to measure spatial forms. By improving local connectivity, accessibility, and pedestrian flow, this method enhances perceptions of diversity, convenience, and navigation, thereby improving user experience. The CICE framework is essential for urban planners in designing human-centred parks. Future research will focus on validating the model through extensive case studies and refining its application for diverse urban contexts.

References

- Douglas O, Lennon M and Scott M (2017). Green space benefits for health and well-being: A life-course approach for urban planning, design and management. *Cities*, 66, 53–62.
- Freeman L C (1979). Centrality in social networks: Conceptual clarification. *Social Networks*, 1(3), 215-239.
- Goličnik B and Ward T C (2010). Emerging relationships between design and use of urban park spaces. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 94(1), 38–53.
- Jordan J S and Knoblich G (2004). Spatial perception and control. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 11(1), 54–59.
- Lynch K (1960). *The image of the city*. The MIT Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts; London, England.
- McCormack G R *et al.* (2010). Characteristics of urban parks associated with park use and physical activity: A review of qualitative research. *Health & Place*, 16(4), 712–726.
- Peters K, Elands B and Buijs A (2010). Social interactions in urban parks: Stimulating social cohesion?. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 9(2), 93–100.
- Proulx M J *et al.* (2016). Where am I? Who am I? The relation between spatial cognition, social cognition and individual differences in the built environment. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7, 64.
- Talen E (2010). The spatial logic of parks. *Journal of Urban Design*, 15(4), 473–491.
- Wang D, Brown G and Liu Y (2015). The physical and non-physical factors that influence perceived access to urban parks. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 133, 53–66.
- You M, Guan C and Lai R (2022). Spatial structure of an urban park system based on fractal theory: A case study of Fuzhou, China. *Remote Sensing*, 14(9), 2144.
- Zhang H *et al.* (2024). Rethinking cultural ecosystem services in urban forest parks: An analysis of citizens' physical activities based on social media data. *Forests*, 15(9), 1633.
- Zhang X, Lu H and Holt J B (2011). Modeling spatial accessibility to parks: a national study. *International Journal of Health Geographics*, 10(1), 31.
- Zhao J, Aziz F A and Ujang N (2024). Factors influencing the usage, restrictions, accessibility, and preference of urban neighborhood parks-A review of the empirical evidence. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 100, 128473.

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